

User Guide:

Creating a Data-to-Knowledge Package

Note: This document is a draft. Please send your questions, comments, and suggestions to [m.konkol\[at\]52north.org](mailto:m.konkol[at]52north.org).

This user guide provides instructions on how to create a Data-to-Knowledge Package (D2K-Package) as described in this [paper](#). We will use the example use case described therein to develop such a package.

Target audience:

Users who have an analysis pipeline (workflow) written in, for instance, R or Python and would like to make it available in a more reproducible and reusable way.

Problem statement:

Publishing and reusing reproducible research is challenging. Users still need to make considerable efforts to understand the data and analysis code before they can reuse parts of the analysis in other contexts.

Solution:

Based on a reproducible basis (code + data + computational environment), further applications including virtual labs, web API services, and workflows are built to provide an entry point to the analysis and encourage reuse. The result is a so-called Data-to-Knowledge Package.

What is a Data-to-Knowledge Package?

The main function of a Data-to-Knowledge Package (D2K-Package) is to link the research components that facilitate the reuse of computational results. At its core, the D2K-Package comprises a reproducible basis including the data and a source code toolbox. This basis enables the derivation of additional research components, such as virtual labs, web API services, and computational workflows.

The D2K-Package promotes the reuse of research materials by enabling researchers to efficiently review, execute and modify analysis workflows. Moreover, its metadata structure ensures findability and accessibility, aligning with the FAIR Principles. Such an approach enhances reproducibility, encourages reusability, reduces redundancy, and ensures synchronization. Do you want to get an impression of a D2K-Package? Visit the [AquaINFRA Interaction Platform](#) and [Zenodo](#).

How can I create a D2K-Package?

Technologies

In this user guide, we propose one possible way to create a D2K-Package but there are many others that will work. For our use case, we use the following technologies to create a D2K-Package:

- [R](#) and [python](#) to write the analysis code
- [conda](#) to specify the libraries
- [GitHub](#) to host the toolbox
 - Note: GitLab is possible, too, but at some point you will need to create a Pull Request to the Galaxy platform, which is only possible via GitHub.
- [Docker](#) to containerize the source code
- [MyBinder](#) to provide the virtual lab
- [OGC API Processes](#) to provide OGC API Web Services based on [pygeoapi](#)
- [OGCAPIProcess2Galaxy tool](#)
- [Galaxy](#) to develop and run workflows
- [ro-crate](#) to create the D2K-Package
- [Zenodo](#) to store the materials

You will need access to a server to host the Docker images encapsulating the code and deploy the OGC API Process using, for instance, pygeoapi. If you are a member of the AqualNFRA project and would like to deploy your processes on the AqualNFRA server, please get in touch with [m.konkol\[at\]52north.org](mailto:m.konkol[at]52north.org).

Step 1: Linking to the input data

A D2K-Package links to all input datasets needed to run the analysis pipeline. A D2K-Package can link to any data that is publicly available via a URL, but never to data that is stored locally on your laptop. The URL can be one that starts the download directly or just redirects to a landing page where the download link is made accessible. Just make sure users can find the actual download link for the data by following your identifier.

Ideally, the links to the datasets are permanent identifiers (e.g., DOIs) and directly lead to downloadable data files. In another scenario, if the data comes from an online service that provides an API requiring query parameters (e.g., OGC API Features service), the D2K-Package should include the full URL with query parameters. Be aware that using URLs instead of DOIs might limit reproducibility as the URL or data might change making the original data inaccessible and the results unreproducible! Alternatively, and if the licence allows it, you can download the data from the service and upload it to a repository of your choice that provides DOIs, e.g., Zenodo.

Some further considerations:

The data should adhere to at least some of the [FAIR Principles](#). To ensure interoperability, data should be stored in text-based formats whenever possible, e.g., CSV and JSON. Binary

formats (e.g., GeoPackage, Shapefile) are acceptable if they follow an open specification. Zipped datasets are also allowed. In the end, however, it is not the D2K-Package that restricts the data format, but your analysis code, which must be able to process the data.

Besides, data should be released under an open license to ensure reusability, preferably CC0. Datasets published under restrictive licenses are excluded. This might also include licenses that restrict modifications, transformations, or derivative works (e.g., CC-BY NoDerivatives). If you're using private or sensitive data, linking to dummy data is recommended (state that clearly!), so others can run the analysis and see how the input data has to look like.

Example data:

- [Input data 1](#) is provided by an OGC API Features service and contains all necessary parameters to query the dataset.
- [Input data 2](#) is a page where users first need to accept the data usage disclaimer before they can copy the URL to the actual data.

To-do if the data is generated by you:

- Publish the data in a data repository of your choice.
- Add metadata to make it better findable.
- Get a public URL, ideally a permanent identifier such as a DOI.
- Release the data under an open license.

To-do if you're using third-party data:

- Collect the links to all input datasets, we will add them later to the D2K-Package.

We will add the input data to the D2K-Package later. If you can't wait and want to see how it looks, check *dataset_1* and *dataset_2* in this [file](#).

Note: Technically, you could simply upload your input data to Dropbox and generate a shared URL. However, this approach is not good scientific practice and not FAIR.

If you're using third-party data, it can happen that the data does not fully comply with the FAIR principles. The second example data, for instance, is not made available under a permanent identifier. In this case you have two options:

Option 1: Use the link as it is and consider that the results might not be reproducible.

Option 2: If the license permits, upload the data to a repository, e.g., Zenodo to get a DOI.

Step 2: Preparing the toolbox

The toolbox contains containerized analysis code (e.g., R or Python) used to generate research results. It includes

- the [code](#), structured into independent and self-contained reusable functions
- a [specification](#) of the computational environment, i.e. runtime and library versions
- a [Dockerfile](#)

Creating reusable functions

Each function should perform a distinct task (e.g., processing, analyzing, or visualizing data) following an input-processing-output logic, meaning that they receive data (e.g., a table or figure) and parameter configurations as inputs, process the data, and produce outputs (e.g., a modified table or figure). The number of functions in a toolbox varies depending on the complexity of the analysis. At a minimum, a single function can encapsulate the entire analysis, but greater reusability is achieved by dividing the workflow into multiple functions that users can call individually and sequentially. Even simple statistical visualizations should be separated into at least two functions: one for statistical computations and another for plotting.

Functions should be designed to accept data links (i.e., URLs) as inputs and return outputs using relative file paths which will later be used by the OGC API Process to generate URLs. In this way, a user can pass the input dataset from a URL to the toolbox function, which reads it, runs some processing or analysis on the data and generates an output path pointing to the output dataset, which can then serve as input for the next function in the workflow. Furthermore, toolbox functions are designed to be independent, meaning they can be called individually. The functions should be stored in separate files and be executable from the outside, e.g., by using command-line-based tools and commands in the form of:

```
R_SCRIPT "toolbox_function1.R" "URL to input dataset_1" "URL to input dataset_2"  
"parameter_1" "parameter_2" "output filename"
```

For a more detailed guide on how to create such reusable functions, check these [slides](#) and the linked example [code](#).

Defining the computational environment

To ensure that the original computational environment can be recreated, the toolbox includes a specification of the runtime (e.g., R version) and a list of required libraries with their versions. All you need to do is create a folder called *.binder* in the toolbox and create the configuration files defining the computational environment *runtime.txt* and *install.R*. In the case of python, do the same with the *environment.yml* (or *requirements.txt* + *runtime.txt*). In R, you can get the library versions on your local laptop using the command “`session.info()`”.

Recommendation for R users: Instead of creating the *runtime.txt* and *install.R* files including libraries maintained by CRAN, we recommend using an *environment.yml* and install the libraries via [Conda](#) (see also [here](#)). Installations via Conda are much faster.

Containerizing the materials

We recommend using Docker to containerize the code and the computational environment. The Dockerfile should be designed to allow users to execute individual functions by specifying the function name as a configuration parameter alongside other input parameters:

```
docker run -it -v ./out:/out -e R_SCRIPT="toolbox_function1.R"  
daugava-workflow-image -- "URL to input dataset_1" "URL to input dataset_2"  
"parameter_1" "parameter_2" "output filename"
```

As you can see in this example [Dockerfile](#), the computational environment defined above is used to create a conda environment. It can also include further dependencies if needed.

Example toolbox:

- [Toolbox](#) containing the functions under */src*, the computational environment under */.binder*, and the Dockerfile.

To-do:

- Fork the toolbox template repository (doesn't exist yet!).
- Create reusable functions and store each function in a separate file under */src*.
- Specify the computational environment under */.binder*.
- Adapt the *Dockerfile* if needed.
- Publish the toolbox on Zenodo to get a DOI (see [GitHub → Zenodo integration](#)).
- Add metadata and an open license to the repository and Zenodo record.

We will add the toolbox to the D2K-Package later. If you can't wait and want to see how it looks, check *toolbox_1* in this [file](#).

Step 3: Creating to a virtual lab

If you successfully managed to create a Toolbox as described in Step 2, you can easily create a virtual lab. Copy the URL of the repository and paste it to the input field of the MyBinder web application. You can also specify the branch or commit if necessary. Based on this information, MyBinder creates a Dockerfile (not the same as the one in the toolbox), builds the image, and launches the container where users can engage with the code more deeply in a ready-to-use virtual lab providing the corresponding programming environment (in this case RStudio). The resulting Binder can be accessed and shared via a URL with other users. For more detailed instructions on using the Binder service, visit their excellent [how-to guide](#) and [get-started introduction](#).

If you paste the URL to MyBinder for the first time, it can take several minutes to launch as MyBinder has to build the image. The next run will be much faster as MyBinder stores the image for a while. Creating a MyBinder is also a final test if you specified the computational environment sufficiently. Otherwise it will not start at all or fail when loading the libraries.

Example virtual lab:

- [Computational environment](#)

- [MyBinder](#)

To-do:

- Copy the repository URL and paste it to the MyBinder UI.
- Copy the resulting MyBinder URL and add a badge to your GitHub repository.

Will add the URL to the MyBinder to the D2K-Package later. Check *virtual_lab_1* in this [file](#).

Step 4: Providing a web API service

You can expose toolbox functions by deploying a web API service using Pygeoapi. This service wraps each toolbox function and builds a Docker command that runs the corresponding containerized function. As a result, each function is accessible via a dedicated OGC API Process endpoint (URL). Users can make a request including input data and parameters to these endpoints from their scripts using HTTP and receive a response with results (e.g., links to tables or figures) for further processing.

For every OGC API Process (one per function) you need to create one python file and one json file including the metadata (inc. title, description, input parameters (data type, default values etc.), and outputs). For a full list of metadata elements, check the [specification](#). These files need to be uploaded to your pygeoapi instance. For more information on how to create

OGC API Processes, check the example [repository](#), example [pygeoapi_server](#) used in AquaINFRA, and the [pygeoapi](#) documentation.

To-do:

- Get a server that meets your requirements.
- Install pygeoapi on that server.
- Create and upload the python and json files defining the process.

Later we will add the URL to the server to the D2K-Package. Check [web_API_service_1](#) in this [file](#).

Step 5: Producing a workflow

To create a workflow you need to integrate your toolbox functions into the Galaxy platform. You have the following options to achieve this:

1. **Create a custom Galaxy tool:** Basically a re-implementation of your function as a Galaxy tool.

Benefits: Runs on Galaxy server and uses its resources. Thus, no server is needed (also works if you don't have a pygeoapi service).

Limitations: Higher workload if you want to integrate several functions → one custom tool per function.

2. **Wrap your pygeoapi server:** This is also a custom tool but all it does is take over the communication with the OGC API Process, hence not a re-implementation.

Benefits: All functions running in your pygeoapi server can be integrated as one tool.

Limitations: The calculations are running on your server. Galaxy only triggers the OGC API Processes. The tool stops working once you shut down your server.

For option 1 there is already enough documentation provided by the Galaxy team. In the following, we focus on the second option, which we successfully implemented in the AquaINFRA project. **Note:** The following steps require a basic understanding of Galaxy tools. We therefore strongly recommend that you read the Galaxy documentation beforehand.

Step 1: The tool [OGC-API-Process2Galaxy](#) generates an XML file as scaffold for a Galaxy tool and an R file in charge of handling requests/responses sent between the Galaxy tool and the OGC API Process. Clone the [OGC-API-Process2Galaxy](#) tool to your local computer and switch to the branch [aquainfra_processes](#). There you will find an [aqua.json](#) file which is the configuration file that you need to adapt as follows (in italic & bold those changes that need to be made by AquaINFRA users):

- Add `server_url`
- Specify processes to be in/excluded (`included_services`, `excluded_services`)
 - * stands for all
- Set an ID, title, and increase the **version number, e.g., from 0.7.0 to 0.8.0**.

- Add only those input parameters to ***input_data_params*** that take a dataset and not just a parameter value.

Then, run the tool using `python3 OGCPProcess2Galaxy.py aqua.json` and check the resulting *generic.xml*. You should now find your processes there in the `select_process` parameter for the dropdown menu in the final tool plus the corresponding input parameters in one of the `<when>` objects below. **Note:** A Galaxy tool XML can be very individual. Hence, the OGC-API-Process2Galaxy tool can only provide a scaffold that you can use as a basis but will likely need to make some adjustments. For example, the tool cannot generate tests or input validators, both need to be created manually.

Step 2: Run a [local Galaxy instance](#) and test your tool there. Alternatively, use our [AqualNFRA Galaxy instance](#) for local testing. See also [this commit](#) where a process was added to the XML file in Galaxy.

Step 3: If it works as expected, create a fork from or branch in <https://github.com/AqualNFRA/tools-ecology>. Go to the file `tools-ecology/tools/aquainfra_ogc_api_processes/aquainfra_ogc_api_processes.xml` and update the xml file with your contribution. Then, make a Pull Request from your tools-ecology branch/fork to <https://github.com/AqualNFRA/tools-ecology>. Once the Pull Request gets accepted, either by you if you have the power, or by one of the AqualNFRA members, you can make a Pull Request to <https://github.com/galaxyecology/tools-ecology>. From here, the Galaxy team will overtake and review the updated tool. Most likely, they will come up with some recommendations. If they agree, the tool will be deployed on the Galaxy platform and become available next Saturday.

Step 4: Once the new or updated tool is on Galaxy, you can start creating your workflow on the platform. Afterwards, publish the workflow file (.ga) on Zenodo or any other repository providing DOIs. Don't hesitate to add metadata, such as a link to the workflow on Galaxy and some instructions on how to run it. See this example [repository](#) on Zenodo.

Later we will add the URL to the workflow to the D2K-Package. Check `computational_workflow_1` in this [file](#).

To-do:

- Integrate toolbox functions into the Galaxy platform.
- Create workflow on the Galaxy platform.
- Publish workflow on Zenodo.

Step 6: Developing a D2K-Package

Creating the D2K-Package is a simple step as you only need to create one file, copy the links to the D2K-Package components to the file, and publish it on Zenodo. We recommend using the tool [Describe](#), a metadata editor for creating linked research objects, but you can also use a simple text editor. As a starting point, you can copy the example D2K-Package file [ro-crate-metadata.json](#) and use it as a D2K-Package template. Keep the name "ro-crate-metadata.json" and store it somewhere locally on your computer. The file describes a D2K-Package composed of two input datasets, one toolbox, one virtual lab, one web API

service, and one workflow. If you have a similar setup, you only need to change the URLs to the components and the metadata in the file. If you have more or less input datasets (or toolboxes or other D2K-Package components), just add or remove them accordingly.

Once you're done with creating the D2K-Package file, you need to publish it on Zenodo. When checking the ro-crate file, you might have noticed that it contains a DOI to the Zenodo record containing the ro-crate file. This can be accomplished by [reserving a DOI](#) before publishing the record. Just copy the reserved DOI to the [ro-crate file](#) and then upload the file to the record. Fill the other metadata (title, authors, descriptions etc.). We recommend adding a few instructions to the description on how to use the D2K-Package, such as how to run the workflow. If you want to make your D2K-Package findable via the [AquaINFRA Interaction Platform](#) (particularly relevant for members of the AquaINFRA project!), you need to add the keyword "Data-to-Knowledge Package" to your record and submit it to the [AquaINFRA community](#).

A D2K-Package must link to at least one toolbox but can also reference toolboxes developed by others if their functions are reused. If a D2K-Package simply reuses existing functions in a new way, creating a new toolbox is unnecessary, links to existing toolboxes suffice. This means a single toolbox can be associated with multiple D2K-Packages. Accordingly, a D2K-Package is not limited to just one workflow, virtual lab, or web API service but can reference several more. However, every workflow step (i.e., toolbox function wrapped as OGC API Process) should be findable in one of the linked toolboxes or on the Galaxy platform.

To-do:

- Create a "ro-crate-metadata.json" file.
- Add links to input datasets, toolbox, virtual lab, web API service, and workflow to the ro-crate file.
- Add further metadata.
- Publish file on Zenodo.

Final [D2K-Package](#).

Updating a D2K-Package

The finalized and published D2K-Package can be updated for various reasons. For some, the effort is minimal, whereas others require fundamental changes to various components. For some, it does make sense to update existing and published D2K-Package, whereas others require the creation of a new D2K-Package, which is way less time-consuming than the first one! Possible scenarios and the required change steps are described below. In any case it is recommended to treat the D2K-Package like a scientific record. For instance, you would probably not want to update a published paper or dataset too often.

- 1) You want to change the metadata of the repository including the D2K-Package file

Let's say you want to update the description of the Zenodo record containing the D2K-Package file. This is not a problem and can just be done on Zenodo ([edit metadata](#)) as

this does not affect any of the D2K-Package components. The same applies to any other components stored on Zenodo.

2) You want to change the metadata in the D2K-Package file

You can do so by changing the `ro-crate-metadata.json` file. This means that you will need to create a new version of the Zenodo record with the updated json file resulting in a new DOI. The old DOI will still redirect to the corresponding version. Users following the old DOI easily also find the new one on Zenodo.

3) You published a paper, poster, talk or similar and would like to add it to the D2K-Package

You can do so by changing the `ro-crate-metadata.json` file and adding another component as you did already with the other D2K-Package components. Tools like Describo can make your work easier and don't forget to look up the right resource type for your new component. You will need to create a new version of the Zenodo record with the updated json file resulting in a new DOI. The old DOI will still redirect to the corresponding version. Users following the old DOI easily also find the new one on Zenodo.

4) The URL to the dataset has changed

All you need to change is the corresponding URL in the `ro-crate-metadata.json` file. This means that you will need to create a new version of the Zenodo record with the updated json file resulting in a new DOI. The old DOI will still redirect to the corresponding version. Users following the old DOI easily also find the new one on Zenodo. However, changing the URL of the dataset should be avoided as much as possible to avoid confusion and effort.

5) You want to change the input parameters of a function in the toolbox

We recommend checking whether the creation of a new D2K-Package is more appropriate, particularly if you already published a paper that links to the D2K-Package. If this is not the case, you will need to walk through the following steps:

1. First, make the required changes to the source code script and get it running locally. Also, test the script by updating the R command.
 - a. Also revise the computational environment.
2. If the code works as expected, rebuild the Docker image and update the Docker command. Run it locally.
3. If the Docker container behaves as expected, update the OGC API Process, i.e., the python file acting as a wrapper and the json file. Run the process locally.
4. If the process works as expected, update the code and Docker image on your server.
5. Update the XML file of the Galaxy tool, test it in your local Galaxy instance, and send a pull request to the Galaxy project. Don't forget to increase the version, e.g., 0.7.0 to 0.7.1.
6. Update the toolbox on Zenodo, rebuild the MyBinder (URL won't change), re-create the workflow on Galaxy, update the workflow on Zenodo.
7. Since the toolbox and the workflow will receive a new DOI, you will also need to update the D2K-Package file. Also this file will get a new DOI that you need to add to the file. You can do so by reserving the DOI. Consequently, everything is transparently tracked, thanks to versioned DOIs ;). If you used a particular GitHub commit to specify the Binder-URL, you will also need to update that URL in the

D2K-Package file. If you used the branch name instead, no changes are needed.
Done!

6) You found a bug in the code

See 5).

7) You want to add a function to the toolbox and use it in the workflow

You have two options: Create a second toolbox and add it to the D2K-Package as described in 3). Or, update the toolbox, virtual lab, OGC API Process, workflow, and the D2K-Package. See also 5).

8) You want to change the library versions in the toolboxes computational environment

See 5).

9) You want to update the pygeoapi server (server URL does not change)

Assuming that the update does not affect the URLs to the server, the processes, the process descriptions, jobs, or results, you will not run into trouble. If you need to make changes to the python scripts that act as wrappers, you can make these changes without touching the Galaxy resources. However, it is strongly recommended to verify that the workflow still works and produces the expected results.

10) You want to deploy the pygeoapi server elsewhere (server URL does change)

The Galaxy tool has an R file in charge of handling requests/responses sent between the Galaxy tool and the OGC API Process. There you need to change the line:

```
server <- "https://aquainfra.ogc.igb-berlin.de/pygeoapi/"
```

Afterwards, you need to update the Galaxy tool.

11) Your Galaxy subdomain is down (e.g., aqua.usegalaxy.eu)

Let's assume the Galaxy subdomain <https://aqua.usegalaxy.eu/> is down. This is not a problem because, as the name suggests, it is just a subdomain of <https://usegalaxy.eu/>, where the tools are still available. You can even make your tools available on other Galaxy instances, such as <https://usegalaxy.org/>. In such cases or if you have doubts, please consult the Galaxy documentation or contact one of the Galaxy maintainers. AquaINFRA users can first contact Markus Konkol (m.konkol@52north.org).